

36TH INTERNATIONAL GEOLOGICAL CONGRESS

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Dear Ms. Lyara Villanova

Congratulations! We are glad to inform you that your abstract has been approved for presentation at the 36th International Geological Congress.

The details submitted by you are as follows:

Presenting author's Name	Ms. Lyara Villanova
Co-Author's Name	Elder Yokoyama Susanne Maciel
Abstract Registration Number - Abstract submission Number	5668 - 5305
Theme	Theme 40: Planetary Sciences Symposium 40.1 Planetary Surface Processes on Moon, Mars and Venus
Title	LUNAR REGOLITH LAYER ESTIMATION USING ACTIVE SEISMIC DATA FROM APOLLO MISSIONS

Abstract:

Over the last 50 years a significant advance in the progress of lunar research was made due to the combination of telescopic, orbital, and surface observations. However, some fundamental scientific questions remain unanswered. One of the important questions to be answered involves the intense dissipation of the seismic waves into the regolith layer. Regolith thickness and its elastic properties have been debated since 1971, when the first results of seismic experiments of the Apollo mission were obtained. The Active Seismic Experiment (ASE) was developed at the Apollo 14, 16 and 17 stations throughout the 1970s. The purpose of ASE was to record seismic waves generated by explosives, thumpers and grenades. The first thickness estimate using these data suggest that regolith layer has 9.5 m to 19 m in depth. Recently, the data obtained from Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter estimated that regolith layer ranges from 2 m to 13 m in thickness. More recently, the Chang'E-3 Lunar Mission provides a new thickness range of this regolith. Chang'E-3 lunar penetrating radar data suggest that regolith layer vary from 5 m to 12.5 m in thickness. In this context, the present study aims to provide a new estimations lunar regolith thickness using different methodologic approaches, such as seismic tomography. In order to compare with previous studies, we used the same ASE data. Consistency and discrepancies between our estimations and previous studies will be discuss.